

Robust Optimization of Filterless Optical Networks with Physical Layer Uncertainties

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Abstract: We propose a robust optimization framework for filterless optical network design in the presence of different levels of physical layer uncertainties. We demonstrate the potential benefits of robustly optimized networks compared to traditional margin-based approaches. © 2025 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

Traditional optical networks use complex and power-hungry equipment to interconnect aggregation points to the hub nodes. Filterless optical networks offer a simpler and more cost-effective solution. Unlike traditional Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM) networks that rely on active Wavelength Selective Switches (WSSs), filterless networks utilize passive splitters and combiners, significantly reducing power consumption and hardware costs. An additional benefit of this architecture is that it matches the upstream aggregation requirements of coherent Point-to-Multipoint (P2MP) transceivers based on Digital Subcarrier Multiplexing (DSCM) [1]. Combined, these solutions minimize the need for expensive electronics, leading to substantial cost savings, lower power requirements, and simplified network management [1]. While amplifiers can be placed at each leaf node, this approach introduces two primary challenges: increased cost and a degradation of the optical signal-to-noise ratio. Hence, the lowest total cost of ownership (TCO) also involves minimizing the required optical amplifiers.

The planning and optimization of optical networks faces challenges. Traditionally, optical communication systems have been designed with considerable margins in key parameters to ensure acceptable quality of transmission (QoT) throughout the network's operational life. This conservative approach, while being effective in maintaining QoT, often leads to increased costs [2]. Recognizing this, substantial efforts have been made to improve QoT predictions and optimize resource allocation, thereby minimizing the need for excessive margins [3]. However, this approach does not address the impact of uncertainties, e.g. on the links, and the resulting differences between the value of parameters assumed during the planning phase and their value in the field and operation.

Fig. 1: Horseshoe topology, leaf node architecture and (a) deterministic ILP formulation, and (b) robust ILP formulation in the presence of links attenuation uncertainties.

Uncertainty can be managed using various strategies. Stochastic optimization incorporates probabilistic models of uncertainty and aims to optimize the expected value of the objective function. When uncertainty is difficult to

model, robust optimization can be more practical and useful despite a higher level of conservatism. It adopts a worst-case strategy, seeking solutions that remain feasible across all values of potential parameters within defined uncertainty sets [4, 5]. On the other hand, sensitivity analysis facilitates the understanding of how variations in parameters affect network design and performance [6]. We use the approach explained in [7] to adapt the integer linear programming (ILP) originally proposed in [1] and create a robust optimization framework. Previously, this mathematical formulation has been successfully exploited in the context of traffic uncertainty [5] and handling failures [8], but it is the first time, to the best of our knowledge, that is applied to design filterless optical networks.

2. Network Architecture and Modeling

The filterless network architecture utilizes a horseshoe topology, with passive couplers performing add/drop functionalities (Fig. 1 (a)). DSCM P2MP transceivers can be deployed at each node. To compensate for optical signal attenuation, EDFAs are strategically placed within the horseshoe to minimize the number of amplifiers. Fig. 1(a) shows the topology and the architecture of the passive nodes. The ILP optimization framework from [1] can optimize this network scenario if uncertainty is ignored. However, uncertainties are always present (even with variable likelihoods), and other factors, such as fiber aging, can add up on top. Therefore, the optimal solution derived from deterministic assumptions may not be directly applicable or feasible in real-world deployment. While adaptive, multi-stage optimization or the common margin-based strategies could be considered, this paper adopts a robust optimization approach to address the challenges posed by link attenuation uncertainties and compare the results with the benchmark margin-based approach. This approach is conservative, as it ensures feasibility under all potential uncertainties (shrunk feasible region), which could lead to a penalty on the objective function.

We modify the ILP model in [1] based on the approach proposed in [7] to optimize the network robustly. Similarly, the objective is to minimize the number of amplifiers, while ensuring the solutions are feasible against all possible realizations of uncertainty within a pre-defined set. In fact, the receiver power sensitivity must be met for all downstream and upstream signals and the launch power level must be limited across all spans to mitigate the impact of nonlinearities. Noteworthy, metro-aggregation network deployment can be subject to cost constraints, and frequent changes and fibers can be installed in diverse locations, subject to different conditions. This limits the ability to have a detailed and accurate characterization of the fiber plant (e.g., span attenuation). For robustness purposes, for every constraint i , we introduce a protection level Γ_i , $i = 0, 1, \dots, m$ that takes values in the interval $[0, |J_i|]$, where $J_i = \{j | \hat{a}_{ij} > 0\}$ (to avoid misunderstandings, we emphasize that this term is distinct from the “protection” term used in the context of survivable networks). For instance, if in a constraint, 6 coefficients are uncertain, Γ can take any values from $[0, 6]$ for that constraint. With $\Gamma = 0$ there will be no protection, and with $\Gamma = 6$, there will be a 100% protection which means the solution will be valid for any combination of links attenuation in the uncertainty range. As depicted in Fig. 1, the robust ILP formulation embeds uncertainties in the constraints. We assume that the uncertainty of the data affects only the elements of the matrix A . This is modeled as follows, $a_{ij} \in [a_{ij} - \hat{a}_{ij}, a_{ij} + \hat{a}_{ij}]$, where \hat{a}_{ij} specifies the uncertainty range. Note that not all uncertainties negatively impact the solution. However, the robust approach can ensure that if uncertainties behave within the modeled range, with the maximum protection solutions will always remain feasible deterministically.

3. Results and Discussion

P2MP transceivers employing dual-polarization 16-QAM modulation were considered in a 400G module with 16 subcarriers (SCs) at 4 GBaud. A minimum receiver input power of -24 dBm per SC was set, while the launch power for leaf and hub nodes was fixed at -12 dBm per SC. To ensure a negligible impact of fiber nonlinearities, the launch power threshold was set to -8 dBm per SC, with a maximum allowable SC power difference at the hub’s receiver of 8 dB. A total of 100 8-leaf networks were assumed in which all links were composed of single-mode fiber pairs with a loss of 0.24 dB/km and an average length of 12 km. Available coupler ratios included the set of [70/30, 90/10]% and the set of [10/90, 20/80, ..., 50/50]% (All). The amplifiers’ minimum and maximum gains were set to 10 dB and 20 dB, respectively. We model link attenuation uncertainty as a uniform distribution with a range of 10% and 15%. Taking 10% as an example, links attenuation could be randomly up to 10% higher or lower than the estimated value.

Fig. 2 shows the infeasible solutions in percentage and the average number of amplifiers obtained by simulating and optimizing 100 networks for “All” and “70/30 & 90/10” coupler ratios when the protection level increases from the minimum of $\Gamma = 0$ to a maximum of $\Gamma = 9$. For each network, we optimize it and then evaluate its performance with randomly changing attenuation values within the defined ranges of uncertainty. If the solution meets all the required conditions, we consider it feasible; otherwise, it is not. Fig. 2(a) assumes 10% uncertainty while Fig. 2(b) considers a 15% uncertainty. The infeasibility rate rapidly decreases as the protection level increases, approaching zero for $\Gamma \geq 4$ (note that we simulated 100 networks, increasing the number of simulations to 1,000 or even 10,000 would allow for a more precise characterization of even the smallest percentages). The average number

of amplifiers rises by 1 to 2 amplifiers. The “All” coupler configuration offers a wider range of possibilities and generally leads to better control over power distribution and more optimal outcomes. Nevertheless, the relative advantage over “70/30% & 90/10%” decreases with higher protection levels due to its increased sensitivity to uncertainties in the network. In the case of 15% uncertainty, the robust model cannot generate a feasible solution for $\Gamma > 4$. However, given the significantly larger uncertainty range, the likelihood of this worst-case outcome is extremely low and infeasibility rate already is extremely low.

Fig. 2: Infeasible solutions percentage versus the protection level for “All” and “70/30 & 90/10” coupler ratios for (a) 10% and (b) 15% uncertainty ranges.

Fig. 3 compares the robust design approach with the traditional margin-based method. Considering no margin and no robustness (baseline) provides the most optimal solutions in terms of the number of amplifiers (Fig. 3(a)) but the chance of infeasibility is as high as 80% with 15% uncertainty range and “All” coupler ratios (Fig. 3(b)). With a 2 dB nonlinearity power margin or sensitivity power margin, the chance of infeasibility decreases to a minimum of 9% but the number of amplifiers rises to a level offered by the proposed robust approach with zero or near-to-zero infeasibility probability.

Fig. 3: (a) Average number of amplifiers for four different optimization approaches in the presence of uncertainty and (b) their corresponding infeasible solutions rate.

4. Conclusion

The proposed robust optimization framework demonstrated its effectiveness in mitigating link attenuation uncertainties. The results showed that robust design offers a better balance between minimizing the number of amplifiers and ensuring feasibility, outperforming traditional margin-based approaches.

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